

Integrating Innovative Biological Research Data into Biostatistics at Two HBCUs

Thomas Gross¹, Xinyao Yang², Dafeng Hui³
Qingxia Li⁴

¹Department of Psychology, Appalachian State University, 287 Rivers Street, Boone, NC 28608

²Department of Applied Mathematics, Xi'an Jiaotong Liverpool University, 111 Ren'ai Road, Suzhou, Jiangsu Province, China, 215123

³Department of Biological Sciences, Tennessee State University, 3500 John A. Merritt Boulevard, Nashville, TN, 37209

⁴Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, 1000 17th Avenue North, Nashville, TN 37208

Abstract

This study examined the impact of a research-embedded flipped classroom biostatistics course that incorporated a formative evaluation process to enhance instructional effectiveness. The investigation focused on three outcomes: biostatistics knowledge, desire for a STEM research career, and attitudes toward STEM courses. Participants were 345 undergraduate students enrolled across three cohorts at two Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs). Using a pre–post design, biostatistics knowledge was assessed through a quiz, while the Career Interest Questionnaire (CIQ) and STEM Semantics Survey (STEMSS) measured changes in career interest and STEM attitudes. Formative evaluation feedback informed iterative refinements of the flipped classroom design across cohorts. Results indicated a significant overall increase in biostatistics knowledge, $t(331) = 3.02, p = .003, d = 0.33$, with Cohort 3 demonstrating the greatest improvement, $F(1, 327) = 20.70, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .06$. Non-significant pre–post differences were observed for CIQ and STEMSS total scores, although cohort-level differences emerged for perceived support and the importance of science careers. Notably, students reported slightly less positive perceptions of STEM careers at post-test, $F(1, 307) = 8.01, p = .005, \eta_p^2 = .03$. Overall, incorporating formative evaluation into the flipped classroom model yielded modest yet meaningful gains in biostatistics knowledge, particularly when implemented with the third cohort. This highlights the potential of iterative instructional design to strengthen biostatistics knowledge, while indicating a need for additional strategies, such as mentorship and explicit career connections, to enhance affective engagement and sustained interest in STEM research pathways.

Key Words: Flipped classroom, formative evaluation, biostatistics education, STEM attitudes, undergraduate research

1. Introduction

The exponential growth of large datasets across natural and social sciences has transformed how new knowledge is created through data examination and analysis. Within the biological sciences, the emergence of the ‘omics’ era has amplified the importance of biostatistics, which informs research design, data analysis, and interpretation of results (Windish, Huot & Green, 2007). Despite this growing significance, many undergraduates, particularly those from underrepresented groups, lack confidence and competence in applying biostatistical methods (Bland, 2004). Strengthening students’ understanding of statistical concepts is therefore essential to diversifying the STEM workforce and equipping undergraduates with the quantitative reasoning skills necessary for modern research careers.

Multiple national programs have demonstrated the transformative impact of introducing undergraduates, particularly those from groups historically underrepresented in science, to authentic research experiences. Notable examples include the Meyerhoff Scholars Program at the University of Maryland, Baltimore County (Maton, Hrabowski & Schmitt, 2000), the Undergraduate Research Opportunities Program (UROP) at the University of Michigan (Nagda et al., 1998), and the Significant Opportunities in Atmospheric Research and Science (SOARS) program at the National Center for Atmospheric Research (SOARS, 2007). These initiatives, among others, have shown that participation in faculty-mentored research enhances students' confidence, increases their retention in STEM fields, and promotes progression into graduate study (Handelsman et al., 1997, 2005, 2007; Hanauer, 2006).

Building on this evidence, early and frequent exposure to authentic research has been shown to increase students' interest and persistence in STEM (Lopatto, 2007; Boyd & Wesemann, 2011). Such experiences cultivate critical thinking, problem-solving, and self-efficacy, allowing students to integrate classroom knowledge into real-world contexts (Osborn & Karukstis, 2009). Furthermore, the accelerated pace of discovery in STEM disciplines underscores the need for educational strategies that allow students to engage as practicing scientists (Withers & Detwiller-Bedell, 2010; Buck, Bretz, & Towns, 2008). Even for students who do not pursue scientific careers, participation in undergraduate research fosters analytical reasoning and lifelong learning (Gregerman, 2003).

Traditional instruction in biostatistics often emphasizes computational procedures rather than scientific inquiry. Yet, effective education in the natural and quantitative sciences requires developing students' capacity to ask meaningful questions, analyze data critically, and interpret findings in context. Embedding authentic research within a biostatistics course provides a mechanism for students to act as "practicing scientists," thereby strengthening both conceptual understanding and engagement in STEM (Weisserger et al, 2016).

To achieve these outcomes, this study implemented and evaluated a research-embedded, flipped-classroom biostatistics course at two Historically Black Universities (HBCUs). The flipped model integrates brief, targeted instructional videos with in-class problem-solving, collaborative inquiry, and research-based projects (Bergmann & Sams, 2008, 2012). This approach increases opportunities for guided practice and application of biostatistical concepts to authentic datasets. Previous studies have demonstrated that flipped instruction can enhance student attitudes toward statistics and improve learning outcomes (Carlson & Winquist, 2011; Peterson, 2016), though findings on performance have been mixed (Gundlach et al., 2015).

The research-embedded course at the HBCUs was designed with two goals: (1) to use biostatistics as an introduction for students to experience scientific discovery through the analysis of socially and biologically relevant data, and (2) to build foundational research skills that foster persistence in STEM education and careers. The overall design of this research-embedded Biostatistics course was composed of four elements: 1) traditional but short (5~10 min) faculty-driven information sharing about the principles of statistics complemented with 'live' demonstrations that are provided in a fully flipped classroom; 2) hands-on practice on genuine research projects/term projects in biostatistics; 3) in-class small group discussions; and 4) course-associated projects. The course-associated projects for this research-focused Biostatistics course incrementally prepared students to engage in formulating their own research questions, sorting and 'cleaning' the data, conducting the data analysis and interpreting the results. The research-associated computer labs familiarized students with use of a computational statistic's 'toolbox' and statistical software to conduct data analysis. We applied 'real world' data under study by the universities' faculty in biological and ecological sciences as 'data projects' to analyze as projects in this course.

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the impact of a research-embedded flipped classroom biostatistics course when using a formative evaluation process. We were interested in outcomes related to biostatistics knowledge, desire for a STEM research career, and attitudes toward STEM

courses. The research questions were: (a) Will the use of a formative evaluation process correspond to increased biostatistics knowledge? (b) Will the use of a formative evaluation process correspond to increased desire for a STEM research career? And (c) Will the use of a formative evaluation process correspond to increased positive attitudes toward STEM courses? To do this, we engaged in the use of formative evaluations to related to procedures for implementing the flipped classroom approach. Outcomes for biostatistics knowledge quiz, and rating scales were used to assess desire for a STEM research career and attitudes toward STEM courses using a pre-post design.

2. Method

2.1 Participants

Participants included 345 students at two HBCU's enrolled in a biostatistics course across three cohorts. The mean age was 20.73 (SD = 2.06). There were non-significant differences between cohorts at pre-post collection, $F(2, 337) = 0.16$, $p = .852$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$. The mean high school grade point average (GPA) was 3.54 (SD = 0.43). There were non-significant differences between cohorts at pre-post collection, $F(2, 337) = 0.24$, $p = .784$, $\eta_p^2 < .01$. The majority of students identified as female (76%), Black or African American (94%), and were biology majors (93%). Five percent identified as Hispanic.

2.2 Measures

2.2.1 Biostatistics quiz

The biostatistics quiz included 20 items that integrated conceptual and technical knowledge, and were directly related to course content. The items were in multiple choice format with four possible answers to select as the response. Each item was worth one point, correct items were summed, and the biostatistics quiz score could range from 0 to 20 points total. McDonald's omega (ω) was used to assess internal consistency for pretest ($\omega = .75$) and posttest (.84) collections, and was found acceptable.

2.2.2 Career Interest Questionnaire (CIQ)

The CIQ contained 12 items that measured interests and supports for a STEM career (Knezek & Christensen, 2008). The items were rated from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree, where a greater score indicated greater interest and perceived support for a STEM career. The CIQ included the three subscales Supportive environment (4 items); Interest in educational opportunities (5 items); and Importance of science career (3 items). It also has a Total score. The subscales and Total score are computed by summing respective items. McDonald's ω was calculated and found adequate internal consistency at pre-test for Supportive environment ($\omega = .74$), Interest in educational opportunities ($\omega = .93$), Importance of science career ($\omega = .80$), and the Total score ($\omega = .92$). Similar results were found for post-test for Supportive environment ($\omega = .85$), Interest in educational opportunities (.96), Importance of science career (.93), and the Total score (.96).

2.2.3 STEM Semantics Survey (STEMSS)

The STEMSS contained 25 items that measured positive perceptions of STEM fields (Knezek & Christensen, 2009). Items were rated on five bipolar pairs from 1 to 7 for Mundane to Fascinating; Unappealing to Appealing; Unexciting to Exciting; Means Nothing to Means A Lot; and Boring to Interesting. There were five separate scales for Science, Math, Engineering, Technology, and Career. McDonald's ω was calculated and found adequate internal consistency at pre-test for Science ($\omega = .86$), Math (.89), Engineering (.86), Technology (.85), and Career (.92). Similar results were found for post-test for Science ($\omega = .88$), Math (.82), Engineering (.79), Technology (.83), and Career (.90).

2.3 Design

A pre-post between-cohorts comparison design (2 x 3 factorial design) was employed to analyze program outcomes. This approach was selected to make full use of available data, particularly because matched samples across years were inconsistent or incomplete. By using a factorial design rather than a repeated-measures approach, the analysis could include all participants with either pre-

or post-test data, thereby maximizing statistical power and generalizability. Additionally, factorial designs tend to yield more conservative estimates of effects, since they require larger and more robust differences to reach statistical significance. In this design, Factor 1 represented the testing period (pre-test vs. post-test), while Factor 2 represented the program cohort, consisting of three independent groups corresponding to the three consecutive years of program implementation. This structure allowed examination of both main effects (time and cohort) and potential interaction effects between time and cohort to assess whether program impact varied across years.

2.4 Procedures

2.4.1 Recruitment and Consent

Participants in this study were recruited from students enrolled in a biostatistics course across three consecutive cohorts at two HBCUs. All students enrolled in the course were invited to participate in the study. Prior to data collection, students were informed about the purpose and procedures of the study, their voluntary participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Those who agreed to participate provided written informed consent at the beginning of the semester, in accordance with Institutional Review Board (IRB) protocols approved by both participating institutions.

2.4.2 General Procedures

The primary outcome measures were administered at the beginning and end of the semester to students enrolled in the respective Biostatistics courses at each university. The course sections were taught using the same materials. At the end of each spring semester, the outcomes data were reviewed with the project team. Each meeting consistently followed the process, whereby, (a) the outcomes data were reviewed, (b) project team members provided information regarding effective and ineffective instructional strategies, and (c) strategies were suggested to augment the program.

2.4.3 Cohort 1

This cohort represented the initial implementation of the flipped classroom approach within the course. While the core instructional materials including assignments, projects, and examinations remained consistent with those used in the traditional format, the mode of instruction was substantially restructured. Students were introduced to SAS software (SAS Institute) as the primary statistical software for conducting analyses and completing coursework. Rather than relying on traditional lectures, students engaged with the foundational course content through a series of short, instructor-recorded online videos that provided conceptual explanations and demonstrations of statistical methods. This asynchronous learning component allowed students to review material at their own pace prior to class meetings. During in-person sessions, class time was reallocated to active learning activities, including guided data analysis exercises, interpretation of statistical output, and collaborative problem-solving using SAS. This approach aimed to promote deeper conceptual understanding and practical skill development through hands-on application. However, some variability in implementation occurred across university programs participating in the study, particularly in the consistency of student engagement and adherence to the flipped classroom format. These differences were primarily related to how instructors structured in-class interactions and managed student participation throughout the course.

2.4.4 Cohort 2

The core materials and strategies remained the same as with Cohort 1. The same assignments, projects, examinations, and use of SAS as the primary statistical software were maintained to ensure comparability across cohorts. To enhance student participation and motivation, course instructors introduced additional engagement incentives, such as opportunities to earn extra credit for completing optional learning activities or demonstrating consistent effort in reviewing course materials. However, there was a notable instructional variation within this cohort: one set of course sections was taught by a different instructor because the primary instructor was on sabbatical during that academic term. While efforts were made to maintain uniformity in course content and assessment, differences in teaching style, communication, and classroom management may have introduced some variability in the student learning experience across sections.

2.4.5 Cohort 3

The core materials and strategies remained the same as with Cohort 1. However, Students were taught to use StatCrunch (Pearson Education Inc., 2025) as the primary statistical software. StatCrunch has additional companion videos for running and interpreting analyses. In-class time contained additional content reviews along with instructor directed analyses and interpretations of them via StatCrunch. Course instructors continued to provide incentives through extra credit for engagement with the course material.

2.5 Analysis Plan

2.5.1 Biostatistics quiz

An intent to treat analysis was completed using an independent samples t-test for pretest compared to post-test on the biostatistics quiz. Biostatistics quiz pre-post outcomes across cohorts were compared using a 3 x 2 analysis of variance (ANOVA). Simple main effects were used to examine relative growth within cohorts and Bonferroni post-hoc paired comparisons were used to examine mean differences across cohorts at each time period.

2.5.2 CIQ

A 3 x 2 Wilk's multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was used to compare pre- and post-test outcomes across cohorts on the CIQ subscales. Main effects comparisons were used to examine relative growth in interests and supports for a STEM career. Bonferroni post-hoc paired comparisons were used to examine mean differences across cohorts at each time period. The CIQ Total score pre-post outcomes across cohorts were compared using a 3 x 2 analysis of variance (ANOVA). Simple main effects were used to examine relative growth within cohorts and Bonferroni post-hoc paired comparisons were used to examine mean differences across cohorts at each time period.

2.5.3 STEMSS

A 3 x 2 Wilk's multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was used to compare pre- and post-test outcomes across cohorts on the STEMSS subscales. Main effects comparisons were used to examine relative growth in interests and supports for a STEM career. Bonferroni post-hoc paired comparisons were used to examine mean differences across cohorts at each time period.

3. Results

3.1 Biostatistics Quiz

Overall, participants had an increase in their biostatistics knowledge, $t(331) = 3.02$; $p = .003$; Cohen's $d = 0.33$, with a small effect. When examining outcomes by cohort, there was a significant interaction between pre-post test collection and cohort, $F(2, 327) = 8.01$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .05$, with a small effect. There was a significant increase in biostatistics knowledge for Cohort 3, $F(1, 327) = 20.70$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .06$, with a small effect. For Cohort 3, there was a mean difference of 3.06, 95% C.I. [1.74, 4.39], or 15% greater score at post-test. There were non-significant changes in scores for Cohort 1, $F(1, 327) = 2.49$, $p = .116$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$, and Cohort 2, $F(1, 327) = 2.59$, $p = .108$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$.

3.2 CIQ

There was a non-significant interaction between time period and cohort on the CIQ subscales, $F(6, 640) = 0.58$, $p = .748$, Wilk's $\Lambda = .99$. However, there was a significant main effect for cohort, $F(6, 640) = 2.24$, $p = .038$, Wilk's $\Lambda = .96$. Specifically, there were significant cohort effects on Supportive environment, $F(2, 322) = 4.17$, $p = .016$, $\eta_p^2 = .03$, with a small effect; as well as, Importance of science career, $F(2, 322) = 3.52$, $p = .031$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$, with a small effect. Bonferroni paired comparisons indicated that Cohort 1 score higher than Cohort 3 for Supportive environment, $M_{\text{difference}} = 1.23$, 95% C.I. [0.19, 2.26], $p = .014$. Non-significant cohort differences on Importance of science career were found after using a Bonferroni paired comparisons between Cohort 1 and Cohort 3, $M_{\text{difference}} = -0.15$, 95% C.I. [-0.97, 0.68], $p = .114$. The detected difference from the main effects were more likely attributable to common variance. There was a non-significant interaction

between time period and cohort on the CIQ Total score, $F(2, 325) = 0.50, p = .609, \eta_p^2 = .003$, as well as non-significant main effects.

3.3 STEMSS

There was a non-significant interaction between time period and cohort on the STEMSS scales, $F(10, 606) = 1.39, p = .179$, Wilk's $\Lambda = .96$. There was a significant main effect from pre- to post-test, $F(5, 303) = 2.31, p = .045$, Wilk's $\Lambda = .96$. A significant difference for pre- to post-test was found on Career, $F(1, 307) = 8.01, p = .005, \eta_p^2 = .03$, with a small effect. Pretest mean score was greater than at post-test, $M_{\text{difference}} = 0.41 [.12, .69], p = .005$. That is, STEM careers were viewed less positively by a small amount.

4. Discussion

Overall, there was a slight but meaningful increase in biostatistics knowledge for participants. When examining biostatistics knowledge across cohorts, Cohort 3 demonstrated relatively greater pre- to post-test scores. This might indicate that the formative changes could have resulted in improved performance from the beginning to end of the biostatistics course. Despite these gains in content knowledge, the outcomes indicated that there were no differences perceptions of STEM careers across time by cohorts. However, Cohort 1 perceived more support for STEM careers than Cohort 3. Further, there was no difference over time by cohort for support within STEM fields, but participants had a general decrease in positive perceptions of STEM careers from the start to end of the biostatistics course.

4.1 Biostatistics Knowledge

These results are consistent with previous studies showing that iterative instructional improvements and active learning strategies can lead to incremental, but sustained gains in quantitative reasoning and statistical literacy among undergraduates (Carlson & Winkvist, 2011; Peterson, 2016). Previous performance increases in statistical knowledge from a flipped-classroom approach indicated mixed results (Gundlach et al., 2015). However, the results of this study could shed light on to how to meet the developmental level of students in a introductory biostatistics course. The initial use of SAS for analyses required students to learn the fundamentals of the statistical analyses, as well as learn syntax specific to SAS. However, StatCrunch provided a graphic user interface, which allowed for placement of variables into conceptual areas, such as independent and dependent variables. StatCrunch provided additional support videos for using the software for various analyses. This could have allowed students to more quickly connect conceptual areas to the analyses they completed. Further, this software might have reduced additional mental effort required to learn additional syntax and connect the syntax to conceptual and procedural aspects for analyses.

4.2 Desire and Attitude Toward STEM Courses and Careers

The desire and attitudes toward STEM courses and careers remained stagnate for the most part. The authentic experiences via real data sets might need additional bolstering. Where others found that authentic experiences increased course and career interest (Lopatto, 2007; Boyd & Wesemann, 2011), we found globally no change. In fact, overall, there was a slight decrease in career interest. It could be engaging students in authentic experiences might include actual data sets, but inclusion related to experimental design and statistical analyses selection, too. This might be more in line with the notion of faculty mentored experiences (Handelsman et al., 1997, 2005, 2007; Hanauer, 2006), as the student-faculty collaboration might be more robust. This could be joined with examples of how the skills learned directly translate to career opportunities within the scope of their desired careers. These examples could include research and other professional careers, for instance medicine.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight both the promise and complexity of integrating authentic research experiences into required quantitative courses. The slight increase in biostatistics knowledge supports the effectiveness of the research-embedded, flipped-classroom model in

promoting conceptual understanding under specific instructional circumstance. Yet, the mixed patterns in STEM attitudes suggest that knowledge gains do not always translate into desired affective or motivational changes. Sustained mentorship, explicit discussion of research career pathways, and greater emphasis on relevance to students' disciplinary interests may help reinforce the connection between skill development and long-term career aspirations.

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